

MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL BASIS OF RESISTANCE AGAINST LEAF FOLDER IN RICE

Thorat S S^{1*}, Sisodiya D B² and Gangwar R K¹¹Main Rice Research Station, Anand Agricultural University, Nawagam, Kheda, Gujarat-387 540, India²Department of Agricultural Entomology, B. A. College of Agriculture,

Anand Agricultural University, Anand, Gujarat-388 110, India

sanjuthorat2@aau.in

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Abstract

The field experiment on morphological and biochemical basis of resistance against leaf folder in rice was carried out at MRRS, AAU, Nawagam during Kharif, 2021 and 2022. This study investigates the impact of various plant traits on resistance to leaf folder. At 45 DAT, all tested varieties exhibited <10% leaf damage, categorizing them as resistant (SES 1). However, significant variation in damage levels was observed at 75 DAT. The varieties viz., GAR 13, GAR 14, GAR 22, GR 101, GAR 1 and Jaya continued to exhibit resistance (SES 1), while others, including Pankhali, TN 1, Krishna Kamod and GR 11 showed moderate resistant (SES 3). Morphological traits such as flag leaf length and width, leaf length and width, plant height and panicle length were positively associated with leaf damage, while a higher number of leaves and tillers per hill showed a negative correlation. Trichome density and length also played a key role, with higher densities and longer trichomes being negatively associated with leaf folder damage. In case of biochemical parameters, higher levels of moisture, chlorophyll and total sugar content in both leaves and stems were associated with increased infestation, possibly providing a more favorable environment for leaf folder development. While, phenol content and antioxidant activity were negatively correlated with leaf folder infestation. These findings underscore the importance of both morphological and biochemical factors in breeding rice varieties with enhanced resistance to leaf folder.

Key words: Correlation, biochemical parameter, morphological traits and leaf folder

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a vital cereal crop, serving as the staple food for over 65% of the global population (Mathur *et al.*, 1999). In Gujarat, rice is grown on approximately 0.95 Mha and producing 2.39 MT, with a productivity of 2529.56 kg/ha during 2022-23 (Anonymous, 2024). The warm and humid conditions are necessary for rice growth. It also creates a conducive environment for insect-pests to thrive. More than 100 insect species are recognized as pests of rice, with about 15 being considered major and economically significant (Teng *et al.*, 1993). The rice leaf folder was considered as a minor or sporadic pest in the past in many Asian countries. However, now it has been considered as one of the important insect-pests. The larvae fold the leaves and feed the green tissues of the leaves and cause scorching and leaf drying. Feeding often resulted in stunting, curling or yellowing of plant green foliage (Alvi *et al.*, 2003). This activity disturbs the photosynthesis as well as plant growth and ultimately yield is reduced. The yield loss caused by leaf folder reported to the extent of 5-80% (Kulgagod *et al.*, 2011) in epidemic situation. Resistant varieties possessing various morphological and biochemical characters is one of the options for controlling insect-pests. In rice, leaf hairiness, length and density of trichomes, leaf surface and leaf sheath compactness are associated with resistance (Israel, 1969). Various morphological plant characters like plant height, length of leaf blade, width of leaf blade, number of leaves and tillers per plant, number of trichomes *etc.*, are involved in imparting resistance against major insect-pests in rice. The biochemical factors are affecting insect behavior, physiology and growth (Saxena, 1986). Some biochemical factors are associated with repellence, deterrence or adverse effects on insect-pests. The ability of resistant or moderately susceptible plants to withstand the attack of insect-pests is due to certain biochemical characteristics, which exert unfavorable effects on the insects (Pathak and Saxena, 1976). Hence, present study was conducted on morphological and biochemical basis of resistance against leaf folder in rice.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment on morphological and biochemical basis of resistance against leaf folder in rice was carried out at Main Rice Research Station, Anand Agricultural University, Nawagam during Kharif, 2021 and 2022. The seeds of test varieties were sown on the well prepared nursery bed and raised by adopting all recommended agronomic practices. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with ten varieties and three replications. In the puddled field, 30 days old seedlings of different test varieties were transplanted with 20×15 cm spacing. The transplanting dates of experiments were 20th August, 2021 and 19th August 2022, respectively during both the year.

The experimental plot size was 2.0×4.5 m and it was kept free from any plant protection measures. The observations on infestation of leaf folder were recorded at 45 and 75 days after transplanting (DAT) from 5 randomly selected hills per variety from net plot area. The observations recorded by counting total number of leaves and number of damaged leaves per hill. The data on per cent damaged leaves were calculated. To evaluate the morphological basis of resistance, observations on the different morphological characters of test varieties were recorded from 5 randomly selected hills per variety by adopting the standard method (IRRI, 2013) at 45 and 75 DAT. In order to record observations on trichome density and length on rice leaves, the samples were brought to Entomology Laboratory, MRRS, AAU, Nawagam. Then, it was examined under an upright microscope and observations were recorded by adopting the method described by Maiti *et al.* (1980). The leaf folder infestation in different varieties were scored using Standard Evaluation System (SES) for rice (IRRI, 2013). The biochemical analysis of different rice varieties was carried out at the Department of Biochemistry, B. A. College of Agriculture, AAU, Anand. The samples of rice stems and leaves were collected at 45 (Vegetative stage) and 75 (Reproductive stage) DAT for biochemical estimation. The biochemical analysis was done at different intervals by adopting respective protocols. The chlorophyll content of rice leaves and stems were estimated as per the method described by Hiscox and Israelstam (1979) with some modifications. Total soluble sugars were determined using the phenol-sulphuric acid method as described by Dubois *et al.* (1956). Total phenols were estimated as per the method described by Bray and Thorpe (1954) with some modifications. The total antioxidant potential was estimated separately by the method of Prieto *et al.* (1999). The field data collected during the course of experimentation were subjected to correlation statistical analysis as per the statistical design used, in order to test the level of significance among the various varieties (Steel and Torrie, 1962).

Results and Discussion**Infestation of leaf folder in different rice varieties**

The data revealed that the, lowest infestation was registered in variety GAR 14 (2.11%) at 45 DAT. A significantly higher (7.20%) infestation was recorded in the K. Kamod, which was at par with Jaya, GR 11, Pankhali and TN 1. Based on the SES score (Table 1), initially the infestation of leaf folder was <10%. So, all the tested varieties were categorized under the resistant (R) group with SES 1. The data at 75 DAT revealed that the lowest infestation was registered in varieties GAR 13 (5.19%) and found at par with GAR 14, GAR 22 and GR 101. The significantly higher (11.86%) infestation was recorded in the variety K. Kamod and which was at par with TN 1 and GR 11. Based

on the SES score, the varieties having SES 1 viz., GAR 13, GAR 14, GAR 22, GR 101, GAR 1 and Jaya considered as resistant with 1-10% leaf damage, while remaining varieties having SES score 3 viz., Pankhali, K. Kamod, TN 1 and GR 11 showed leaf folder infestation ranged between 11-20% considered as moderately resistant.

Role of morphological characters of different rice varieties against leaf folder in rice

Leaf length (cm)

The data revealed that at 45 DAT highest leaf lengths were recorded in the varieties (Pankhali (55.77cm), TN 1 and K. Kamod (49.43cm)) having higher leaf damage. While, significantly lowest leaf length ranged (42.50-46.37cm) were noticed in varieties viz., GAR 1, GAR 13, GR 11, GAR 14, Jaya and GR 101. Simultaneously, the varieties GAR 1, GAR 13, GR 101 and GAR 14 recorded minimum infestation of leaf folder. Correlation studies (Table 3) found positively non-significantly correlated with leaf damage ($r=0.517$). The varieties Pankhali, K. Kamod and TN 1, which were moderately resistant, showed the highest ranged of leaf length (58.27-58.87cm), except GR 11 at 75 DAT. On the other hand, significantly lowest leaf length was noticed in resistant varieties i.e., GAR 1, GAR 13, Jaya, GAR 14 and GR 101 (46.93-48.73cm). Correlation studies showing a positive correlation ($r=0.604$) with leaf damage. The present results are corroborated with the findings of Punithavalli *et al.* (2011) who reported that the leaf length might contribute to resistance against leaf folder infestation. However, Nayak *et al.* (2023) reported that rice leaf folder damage was significantly negatively correlated with leaf length.

Leaf width (cm)

The data revealed that the resistant varieties (GAR 14, GAR 1 and GAR 22) had significantly lower leaf width ranged (1.02-1.07cm) and recorded lower leaf damage at 45 DAT. These varieties were at par with K. Kamod and GR 11 having higher leaf damage. The correlation studies show a significant positive correlation ($r=0.702^*$) between leaf width and leaf damage. The data at 75 DAT revealed that the resistant varieties, such as GAR 14 (1.07cm), GAR 1 and GAR 22 (1.17cm) recorded significantly lower leaf widths, which were on par with the moderately resistant varieties i.e., K. Kamod, TN 1, GR 11 and Pankhali exhibited higher leaf widths and found statistically comparable with the resistant varieties Jaya, GAR 13 and GR 101. Correlation studies (Table 3) revealed a positive correlation ($r=0.443$) between leaf width and leaf damage. Previous workers have also reported similar findings. The researchers like Punithavalli *et al.* (2011), Singh (2018), Ashrith *et al.* (2020) and Nayak *et al.* (2023) who noted that leaf width was positively correlated with leaf folder infestation.

Flag leaf length (cm)

The data clearly indicated that the varieties GR 11, Jaya, K. Kamod, Pankhali and TN 1, which have varied flag leaf lengths (31.87-46.07cm), all exhibited higher leaf folder infestations at 45 DAT. The varieties GAR 13, GAR 1, GAR 14, GR 101 and GAR 22, which have varied flag leaf lengths (32.20-37.20cm), all exhibited lower leaf folder infestations. Correlation studies confirmed a positive correlation ($r=0.327$) between flag leaf length and leaf damage. The data of flag leaf length at 75 DAT revealed that the moderately resistant varieties recorded significantly the highest flag leaf length TN 1 (57.87cm), Pankhali and K. Kamod (49.87cm), except GAR 22. While, resistant varieties GAR 13, GAR 14, GR 101, GAR 1 and Jaya, except GR 11 noted significantly lower flag leaf length (40.80-43.47cm). Correlation studies (Table 3) confirmed a positive correlation ($r=0.488$) between flag leaf length and leaf damage.

Flag leaf width (cm)

The data revealed that the varieties like TN 1, Jaya and GR 11, which recorded significantly wider flag leaves (1.35-1.32cm), also exhibited higher infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. Whereas, varieties such as GAR 1 (1.07cm), GAR 14 and GAR 22 (0.93cm) with narrower flag leaves, showed significantly lower leaf folder infestations. Correlation studies confirmed a positive correlation ($r=0.615$) between flag leaf width and leaf damage. The varieties TN 1 and GR 11 recorded wider

flag leaf ranged (1.60-1.65cm) were particularly moderately resistant against leaf folder with higher infestation except, Jaya. Conversely, varieties with narrower flag leaves, such as GAR 22 (1.21cm), GAR 14 and GAR 1, GR 101, GAR 13 (1.49cm) showed resistant to leaf folder with lower infestation except, Pankhali and K. Kamod. Correlation studies (Table 3) showed a positive association ($r=0.407$) between flag leaf width at 75 DAT and leaf damage.

Number of leaves

The varieties i.e., Pankhali, GR 11 and K. Kamod recorded number of leaves 31.57-33.17 and also noted higher infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. While, varieties GAR 13 (37.30), GAR 22, GAR 14 and GR 101 (31.97) recorded significantly lower leaf folder infestations. Correlation studies showed a negative correlation ($r=-0.179$) between the number of leaves and leaf damage. The highest number of leaves was recorded at 75 DAT in GAR 13 (44.13) followed by TN 1, GAR 14, GAR 101, K. Kamod, GR 11, Pankhali, GAR 22, Jaya and GAR 1. The GAR 14, GAR 22, GAR 13, GR 101 and GAR 1 showed resistant to leaf folder with lower infestations. The varieties viz., TN 1, K. Kamod, GR 11 and Pankhali showed moderately resistant reaction with higher leaf damage. Correlation studies (Table 3) confirmed a negative correlation ($r=-0.370$) between the number of leaves and leaf damage.

Number of tillers

The data at 45 DAT indicated that the varieties like GAR 13, GR 101, GAR 14 and GAR 1, which had a significantly higher number of tillers (11.03-9.67), exhibited lower infestations of leaf folder. While, varieties with lower tillers, such as TN 1 (8.33), Pankhali, GR 11, Jaya and K. Kamod (8.67) experienced higher leaf folder infestations. Correlation studies showed a highly significant negative correlation ($r=-0.884^{**}$) between the number of tillers and leaf damage. The moderately resistant varieties viz., GR 11, TN 1, Pankhali and K. Kamod recorded lower number of tillers (9.77-10.0) at 75 DAT. Whereas, resistant varieties viz., GAR 13, GAR 14, GR 101 and GAR 1 recorded more number of tillers (12.60-11.00), except Jaya. Correlation studies (Table 3) revealed a highly significant negative association ($r=-0.859^{**}$) between the number of tillers and leaf damage.

Plant height (cm)

The varieties with lower plant height, such as Jaya (90.23cm), GR 101, GAR 14 and GAR 13 (108.30 cm), demonstrated lower infestation of leaf folder, except GR 11 at 45 DAT. Whereas, the varieties viz., TN 1 (150.13cm), Pankhali and K. Kamod (137.83cm) recorded maximum plant height. These varieties showed significantly higher infestation of leaf folder. Correlations between plant height and leaf folder infestation ($r=0.389$) was positive. The data at 75 DAT revealed that the varieties like GR 101, Jaya, GAR 13, GAR 14, GAR 1 and GAR 22 demonstrated comparatively lower plant heights (97.37-135.40cm) and showed a resistant reaction against leaf folder with lower leaf damage, except GR 11. In contrast, moderately resistant varieties like K. Kamod, Pankhali and TN 1 exhibited relatively higher plant heights (178.00-156.77cm) with higher infestation of leaf folder. Plant height had a positive correlation (Table 3) with the leaf damage ($r=0.514$). These findings aligned with earlier studies carried out by Punithavalli *et al.* (2011) and Singh (2018) who suggested that plant height could contribute to resistance against leaf folder. Nayak *et al.* (2023) found similar relationships for leaf folder damage.

Panicle length (cm)

The data on panicle length at 75 DAT evident that the moderately resistant variety (GR 11) against leaf folder possessed significantly lowest panicle length (20.85cm). Whereas, the highest panicle length noted in TN 1 (29.64cm), GAR 22, Pankhali, K. Kamod, GAR 1, GAR 14 and GR 101 (25.63cm). Among them GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 1 and GR 101 showed resistant reaction while TN 1, Pankhali and K. Kamod showed moderately resistant to leaf folder. Correlation revealed that panicle length had a positively correlation with leaf damage ($r=0.048$). These findings contrast with those of Kumar *et al.* (2021), who reported a significantly negative influence of panicle length on leaf folder infestation.

9. Trichome density (No./cm² leaf area)**Trichome density upper surface leaves (Adaxial)**

The varieties GR 101, GAR 14 and GAR 22, which had significantly higher trichome density (74.20-61.77/cm²) exhibited lower infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. The varieties with lower trichome density, such as Pankhali (8.23/cm²), TN 1 and K. Kamod (13.90/cm²) experienced higher leaf folder infestations. Correlation analysis (Table 3) indicated a highly significantly negative correlation leaf damage ($r=-.837^{**}$). The variety GR 101 exhibited the highest trichome density (84.07/cm²) at 75 DAT, which was statistically on par with GAR 22, GAR 14 and GAR 13. These varieties exhibited resistant reactions with lower infestations of leaf folder. While TN 1, Pankhali, GR 11, K. Kamod and Jaya had lower trichome density (16.53-41.73/cm²). The varieties Pankhali, TN 1, GR 11 and K. Kamod were moderately resistant with higher leaf damage, whereas Jaya gave resistant reactions. Correlation studies revealed highly significantly negative association with leaf damage ($r=-.890^{**}$).

Trichome density lower surface leaves (Abaxial)

The data at 45 DAT revealed that the varieties *viz.*, GR 11, K. Kamod, Pankhali and TN 1 with lower trichome densities (6.63-8.87/cm²) exhibited higher infestations of leaf folder. While, GR 101 (26.20/cm²), GAR 14 and GAR 13 (18.70/cm²), which had higher trichome densities, recorded significantly lower infestations of leaf folder. Confirmed by the correlation studies (Table 3) which revealed highly significantly negative correlation with leaf damage ($r=-.689^{**}$). The leaf folder resistant varieties *viz.*, GR 101, GAR 14, GAR 22, GAR 13 and GAR 1 exhibited the significantly highest trichome density (32.93-12.47/cm²) at 75 DAT. The significantly minimum trichome density was recorded in moderately resistant varieties *viz.*, K. Kamod (8.43/cm²), GR 11, TN 1 and Pankhali (10.63/cm²) except Jaya found resistant. Correlation studies further revealed a highly significantly negative association with leaf damage ($r=-.770^{**}$). The current findings align with previous research carried out by Punithavalli *et al.* (2011) and Ashrith *et al.* (2020), who reported that higher trichome density contributes to resistance against leaf folder infestations in rice.

10. Trichome length (µm)**Trichome length on upper surface leaves (Adaxial)**

The varieties with shorter trichomes *viz.*, Pankhali (205.64µm), TN 1, K. Kamod, GR 11 and GAR 14 (333.41µm) exhibited higher leaf damage at 45 DAT. Conversely, varieties with longer trichomes *i.e.*, GAR 13 (453.00µm), GR 101 and GAR 1 (371.27µm) recorded significantly lower infestations of leaf folder. Correlation studies (Table 3) exerted negative correlation with leaf damage ($r=-.469$). The varieties GAR 14 and GR 101 have the highest trichome lengths (587.83-530.40µm), while TN 1, GAR 22, GR 11, Pankhali and K. Kamod exhibit significantly lower trichome lengths (271.25-312.62µm) at 75 DAT. The rice varieties, Pankhali, TN 1, K. Kamod and GR 11 showed moderately resistant reactions, while GAR 14, GAR 22 and GR 101 exhibited resistant reactions with lower leaf folder infestation. The correlation studies further supported these results and revealed that the significantly negative association between trichome length and leaf folder infestations ($r=-.725^*$).

Trichome length on lower surface leaf (Abaxial)

The varieties with shorter trichome lengths (TN 1 (97.18µm), GR 11, K. Kamod, Pankhali and Jaya (125.72µm)) also showed higher infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. However, varieties with longer trichome lengths (GR 101 (282.45µm) and GAR 14 (238.20µm)) recorded significantly lower infestations of leaf folder. Further supporting these observations, correlation studies (Table 3) demonstrated a highly significantly negative relationship between trichome length and leaf folder infestations ($r=-.786^{**}$). The leaf folder infestation (75 DAT), varieties with longer trichomes (GR 101 (351.71µm), GAR 1 and GAR 14 (317.18µm)) showed resistant reactions, while those with shorter trichomes (K. Kamod (142.09µm), Pankhali, TN 1 and GR 11 (150.90µm)) exhibited moderately resistant reactions. Correlation studies further revealed a highly significantly negative association with leaf folder infestations ($r=-.869^{**}$). The

current findings aligned with the work of Punithavalli *et al.* (2011), who suggested that trichome length contribute to resistance against leaf folder.

Role of Biochemical Content of Different Rice Varieties against Leaf folder in Rice**Moisture (%)****Leaf**

The varieties TN 1, K. Kamod, Pankhali, GR 11 and Jaya recorded significantly higher leaf moisture (81.89-79.65%) and also exhibited higher infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. However, GR 101, GAR 22, GAR 13, GAR 14 and GAR 1 showed significantly lower leaf moisture (71.11-73.52%) and found to have lower damaged leaves. Correlation (Table 5) also revealed that highly significantly positive correlation with leaf damage ($r=.925^{**}$). The varieties, TN 1, K. Kamod, Pankhali and GR 11 with higher leaf moisture (81.95 to 78.46%) showed moderately resistant reaction with higher infestation of leaf folder except, Jaya at 75 DAT. While, the varieties, GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 22, GAR 1 and GAR 14 with lower leaf moisture (68.14-72.03%) exhibited resistant reaction with lower infestation of leaf folder. Correlation exposed highly positively significant correlation with leaf damage ($r=.940^{**}$).

Stem

The varieties (K. Kamod, TN 1, GR 11 and Pankhali) recorded higher moisture (75.91 to 75.11%) showed higher infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. On the other hand, GAR 13, GR 101, GAR 14, GAR 1 and GAR 22 exhibited lower moisture (66.52-63.34%) recorded significantly lower infestations of leaf folder. The moisture content showed highly significantly positive association with leaf damage ($r=.937^{**}$). The varieties with higher moisture content at 75 DAT, such as K. Kamod (75.85%), Pankhali, TN 1, GR 11 and Jaya (73.74%), showed moderately resistant reaction with higher infestation of leaf folder. On the other hand, GAR 22, GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 1 and GAR 14, which had lower moisture content (62.10-66.86%) exhibited resistant reaction with lower infestation of leaf folder. Correlation studies (Table 5) which revealed highly significantly positive correlation with leaf damage ($r=.935^{**}$).

2. Chlorophyll (mg/g fresh wt.)**Leaf**

The data at 45 DAT suggested that varieties with higher chlorophyll content, such as TN 1 (5.29 mg/g), K. Kamod, Pankhali, GR 11 and Jaya (5.0 mg/g) exhibited higher leaf damaged. Whereas, GR 101, GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 13 and GAR 1, which had lower chlorophyll content (2.03-2.49 mg/g) showed significantly reduced leaf damage. Correlation studies which revealed highly positively correlated with leaf damage ($r=.949^{**}$). The data suggested that varieties (TN 1, Pankhali, K. Kamod, GR 11 and Jaya) with higher chlorophyll content (4.48-3.79 mg/g) were moderately resistant reaction with higher leaf damage at 75 DAT. Whereas, GR 101, GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 13 and GAR 1 had lower chlorophyll content (1.92-2.20 mg/g) exhibited resistant reaction with lower leaf damage. Correlation studies (Table 5) showed a highly significantly positive relationship with leaf damage ($r=.959^{**}$).

Stem

The data indicated that rice varieties with higher chlorophyll content, such as TN 1 (4.71mg/g), Pankhali, K. Kamod, GR 11 and Jaya (3.88 mg/g) were more prone to higher leaf damage at 45 DAT. Whereas, varieties like GR 101, GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 13 and GAR 1, which had lower chlorophyll content (1.86-2.46mg/g) showed significantly reduced leaf damage. Correlation studies revealed a highly significant positive association with leaf damage ($r=.928^{**}$). The chlorophyll content at 75 DAT was higher in moderately resistant rice varieties *viz.*, TN 1 (3.78mg/g), Pankhali, K. Kamod and GR 11 (3.39mg/g) against leaf folder. While the chlorophyll content was lower in leaf folder resistant varieties (GR 101 (1.95mg/g), GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 13, GAR 1 and Jaya (3.34mg/g). Chlorophyll content was highly significant and positively (Table 5) correlated with leaf damaged ($r=0.955^{**}$).

3. Total phenols (%)**Leaf**

The varieties with higher total phenol content (GR 101 (0.57%), GAR 13, GAR 14, GAR 22 and GAR 1 (0.39%)) showed significantly lower infestations of leaf folder at 45 DAT. Varieties with lower phenol content (Pankhali (0.15%), K. Kamod, TN 1, GR 11 and Jaya (0.25%)) recorded higher leaf damage. Correlation analysis revealed a highly significantly negative relationship with leaf folder infestations ($r=-.921^{**}$). The rice varieties GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 14 and GAR 22 demonstrated significantly higher total phenol content (0.68-0.61%) at 75 DAT. These varieties also exhibited resistant reaction with lower infestation of leaf folder. Whereas, the varieties Pankhali, K. Kamod and TN 1 recorded significantly lower total phenol content (0.24-0.27%). These varieties also showed moderately resistant reactions with higher leaf folder infestation. Correlation studies (Table 5) exerted highly significantly negative correlation with leaf damage ($r=-.952^{**}$).

Stem

The leaf folder infestations at 45 DAT, the varieties with lower phenol content, such as Pankhali (0.15%), K. Kamod and TN 1 (0.19%) recorded higher leaf damage. Whereas, GR 101 (0.66%), GAR 13 and GAR 14 (0.61%) which had higher phenol content, showed significantly lower infestations of leaf folder. Correlation studies (Table 5) revealed a highly significantly association with leaf folder infestations ($r=-.937^{**}$). The data at 75 DAT revealed that the varieties with lower phenol content, such as Pankhali (0.29%), K. Kamod, TN 1 and GR 11 (0.33%) showed moderately resistant reactions with higher leaf damage of leaf folder except, Jaya (0.37%). Whereas, varieties with higher phenol content, such as GAR 22 (0.77%), GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 1 and GAR 14 (0.79%), were found resistant with lower infestation of leaf folder. Correlation studies revealed that total phenol recorded highly significantly negative association with leaf damage ($r=-.961^{**}$). The current findings have close concern with the findings of Ashrith *et al.* (2020) they reported that phenol in rice was negatively correlated with leaf folder damage. Nayak *et al.* (2023) also revealed that phenol showed significant negative correlation with leaf folder damage. Moreover, Singh (2018) found that phenol content was higher in the leaf folder resistant genotypes. Kumar *et al.* (2021) also observed that the total phenols and ortho dihydroxy phenols found significantly higher in resistant genotypes. These findings are parallel to the current findings.

4. Total soluble sugars (%)**Leaf**

The data suggested that rice varieties like Pankhali, TN 1, K. Kamod, Jaya and GR 11, which had higher total soluble sugar content (5.82-5.25%) at 45 DAT. Which exhibited higher infestations of leaf folder. However, varieties such as GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 22, GAR 14 and GAR 1, with lower soluble sugar content (3.34-3.81%) showed significantly reduced leaf folder infestations. Correlation studies (Table 5) noted highly positively correlated with leaf damage ($r=.924^{**}$). The data at 75 DAT revealed that the varieties Pankhali, TN 1, K. Kamod, Jaya and GR 11 which had significantly higher total soluble sugar (5.84-4.83%) in leaf, showed moderately resistant reaction with higher infestations of leaf folder except, Jaya exhibited resistant reaction. Varieties with lower sugar content, such as GR 101 (2.43%), GAR 13, GAR 22, GAR 14 and GAR 1 (3.08%), demonstrated resistant reactions with lower infestation of leaf folder. Correlation studies revealed highly significantly positive association with leaf damage ($r=.935^{**}$).

Stem

Rice varieties such as Jaya, Pankhali, TN 1, K. Kamod and GR 11 with higher total soluble sugar content (5.62-5.17%) recorded higher leaf damage at 45 DAT. Whereas, GR 101, GAR 22 and GAR 14 had lower total soluble sugar content (3.32-3.52%) showed significantly lower leaf damage. Correlation studies (Table 5) revealed a highly significantly positive association with leaf damage ($r=.929^{**}$). The Pankhali, TN 1 and K. Kamod recorded higher total soluble sugar

(5.29-5.10%) exhibited moderately resistant reactions with leaf damage at 75 DAT. While, GR 101, GAR 22, GAR 13, GAR 1 and GAR 14 had lower total soluble sugar content (2.76-3.02%) demonstrated resistant reactions with lower leaf damage. Correlation analysis indicated a highly significant positive association ($r=.893^{**}$) to leaf damage. According to Ashrith *et al.* (2020) and Patel (2016), total sugar content in rice was significantly positively correlated with leaf damage. These findings aligned with the present investigation. Similarly, Nayak *et al.* (2023) reported that total soluble sugar, total sugars showed a significant positive correlation with leaf folder damage.

Total antioxidant activity (%)**Leaf**

The varieties with lower antioxidant activity, such as Pankhali (0.68%), TN 1, K. Kamod, Jaya and GR 11 (0.78%), exhibited higher leaf damage at 45 DAT. While, varieties with higher antioxidant activity, such as GR 101 (1.14%), GAR 22, GAR 14, GAR 13 and GAR 1 (1.09%), recorded significantly lower damage leaves. The correlation analysis (Table 5) showed highly significantly negative correlation with leaf damage ($r=-.947^{**}$). At 75 DAT varieties with lower antioxidant activity (Pankhali (0.51%), K. Kamod and TN 1 and GR 11 (0.61%)) exhibited moderately resistant reactions except, Jaya. While, those with higher antioxidant activity (GAR 22 (1.07%), GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 1 and GAR 14 (1.12%)) showed resistant reactions with lower leaf damage. Correlation studies revealed a highly significant negative association ($r=-.955^{**}$) with leaf damage.

Stem

The varieties with lower antioxidant activity, such as Pankhali (0.21%), K. Kamod and TN 1 (0.22%) were associated with higher leaf damage at 45 DAT. However, GAR 13 and GR 101 noted total antioxidant activity was much higher (0.83-0.77%), also showed significantly lower infestation of leaf folder. Correlation studies confirmed a highly significant negative correlation ($r=-.936^{**}$) with leaf damage. The GAR 13, GR 101, GAR 14, GAR 22 and GAR 1, which exhibited higher total antioxidant activity (0.55-0.46%), which was also found resistant against leaf folder, except Jaya. While, Pankhali, TN 1, K. Kamod and GR 11, which showed lower antioxidant activity (0.14-0.22%) and found moderately resistant reactions with higher leaf damage. Correlation studies further revealed a highly significantly negative association with leaf damage ($r=-.963^{**}$). Similar findings were reported by Nayak *et al.* (2023), who found that antioxidative enzymes showed a significant negative correlation with leaf folder damage.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that the rice varieties GAR 1, GAR 14, GR 101, GAR 13, GAR 22 and Jaya were found to resistant reaction with lower infestations of leaf folder, while varieties GR 11, Pankhali, Krishna Kamod and TN1 exhibited moderately resistant reactions with higher damage leaves. Key plant traits, such as leaf width, flag leaf width, plant height and trichome density and length, played a critical role in determining resistance. Wider leaves and taller plants were associated with higher infestation levels, while varieties with narrower leaves and higher trichome density, such as GR 101 and GAR 14, showed resistance with lower damage leaves. Leaf moisture and chlorophyll levels were positively correlated with leaf folder damage, with higher values associated to increased susceptibility. Conversely, higher phenol content and antioxidant activity, as seen in resistant varieties like GR 101 and GAR 13, were associated with reduced infestations, showing a highly negative correlation with leaf folder damage.

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Table 1: Reactions of rice varieties against leaf folder (Pooled Kharif, 2021 and 2022)

Vr. No.	Varieties	Leaf damage (%) at indicated days after transplanting		Reactions of varieties at indicated days after transplanting			
		Pooled		45		75	
		45	75	SES score	Reactions	SES score	Reactions
V ₁	GAR 1	11.79 ^b (4.18)	15.16 ^b (6.84)	1	R	1	R
V ₂	GAR 14	8.35 ^a (2.11)	14.13 ^{ab} (5.96)	1	R	1	R
V ₃	GR 101	12.34 ^b (4.57)	14.87 ^{ab} (6.58)	1	R	1	R
V ₄	Pankhali	16.30 ^c (7.88)	20.05 ^{cd} (11.76)	1	R	3	MR
V ₅	Krishna Kamod	15.57 ^c (7.20)	20.15 ^d (11.86)	1	R	3	MR
V ₆	GR 11	16.28 ^c (7.85)	20.92 ^d (12.75)	1	R	3	MR
V ₇	GAR 13	10.79 ^b (3.50)	13.17 ^a (5.19)	1	R	1	R
V ₈	Jaya	15.73 ^c (7.35)	18.06 ^c (9.61)	1	R	1	R
V ₉	GAR 22	10.90 ^b (3.58)	14.41 ^{ab} (6.19)	1	R	1	R
V ₁₀	TN 1	16.38 ^c (7.95)	20.88 ^d (12.70)	1	R	3	MR
SEm±		V	0.65				
		Y	0.29				
		V × Y	1.12				
CD at 5%			Sig.				
CV (%)			11.77				
			8.88				

Note: Figures in parenthesis are retransformed values and those outside are arcsine transformed values; R- Resistant; MR- Moderately Resistant; V- Variety and Y- Year

Morphological characters of leaves rice varieties at different growth stages (Pooled Kharif, 2021 and 2022)

Vr. No.	Varieties	Leaf length (cm)		Leaf width (cm)		Flag leaf length (cm)		Flag leaf width (cm)		Number of leaves/ hill		Number of tillers/ hill		Plant height (cm)		Panicle length (cm)	No. of trichomes/ cm ² leaf area				Trichome length (µm)				
		45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT		75 DAT	Trichome density upper surface leaves (Adaxial)		Trichome density lower surface leaves (Abaxial)		Upper surface leaves (Adaxial)		Lower surface leaves (Abaxial)	
																		45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT
V ₁	GAR 1	42.50 ^a	46.93 _a	1.04 ^a	1.15 ^{ab} _c	32.23 ^a _b	43.1 ₇ ^a	1.07 _{ab}	1.36 ^a _{bc}	30.5 ₇	35.1 ₀	9.67 ^{ab} _c	11.00 _{bc}	118.87 ^c _d	133.17 _d	26.04 ^c _d	25.90 ^c _d	44.13 _c	10.53 ^c	12.4 ₇ ^c	371.27 _{ab}	456.77 _{bc}	194.86 _{bc}	328.90 ^a	
V ₂	GAR 14	44.17 ^a _{bc}	48.37 _a	1.02 ^a	1.07 ^a	32.77 ^a _b	41.7 ₃ ^a	1.04 _{ab}	1.36 ^a _{bc}	32.1 ₃	37.8 ₀	10.30 _{ab}	12.07 _{ab}	104.07 ^a _{bc}	116.83 _c	25.96 ^c _d	69.83 ^a _b	77.77 _a	19.53 ^b	22.9 ₇ ^b	333.41 _b	587.83 _a	238.20 _{ab}	317.18 ^a	
V ₃	GR 101	46.37 ^a _{bc}	48.73 _a	1.13 ^a _{bc}	1.23 ^{ab} _{cd}	33.93 ^a _{bc}	42.3 ₃ ^a	1.11 _b	1.46 ^c _d	31.9 ₇	37.6 ₇	10.40 _{ab}	12.03 _{ab}	90.67 ^a	97.37 ^a	25.63 ^c _d	74.20 ^a	84.07 _a	26.20 ^a	32.9 ₃ ^a	402.77 _{ab}	530.40 _{ab}	282.45 _a	351.71 ^a	
V ₄	Pankhali	55.77 ^d	58.87 _c	1.19 ^b _c	1.27 ^{bc} _d	36.20 ^b _c	50.4 ₇ ^b	1.11 _b	1.39 ^b _c	31.5 ₇	36.6 ₀	8.47 ^c	10.03 _c	143.70 ^f	161.20 _e	27.46 ^a _b	8.23 ^d	24.50 _{de}	8.53 ^c	10.6 ₃ ^c	205.64 _c	296.85 _d	124.40 _{de}	147.49 ^c	
V ₅	Krishna Kamod	49.43 ^b _{cd}	58.67 _c	1.03 ^a	1.11 ^{ab}	34.03 ^a _{bc}	49.8 ₇ ^b	0.98 _{ab}	1.28 ^a _b	33.1 ₀	36.7 ₇	8.67 ^c	10.00 _c	137.83 ^{ef}	178.00 _f	26.32 ^c _d	13.90 ^c _d	32.00 _{cd}	7.23 ^c	8.43 ^c	226.51 _c	312.62 _d	121.15 _{de}	142.09 ^c	
V ₆	GR 11	43.43 ^a _{bc}	47.13 _a	1.25 ^c	1.36 ^d	31.87 ^a	41.0 ₇ ^a	1.32 _c	1.65 ^e	33.1 ₇	36.7 ₃	8.50 ^c	9.77 ^c	102.20 ^a _b	111.37 _{bc}	20.85 ^e	23.70 ^c _d	25.53 _{de}	6.63 ^c	8.87 ^c	228.63 _c	289.70 _d	109.11 _{de}	150.90 _{bc}	
V ₇	GAR 13	43.33 ^a _b	47.33 _a	1.15 ^a _{bc}	1.33 ^{cd}	32.20 ^a	40.8 ₀ ^a	1.13 _b	1.49 ^c _{de}	37.3 ₀	44.1 ₃	11.03 _a	12.60 _a	108.30 ^b _{cd}	112.67 _{bc}	22.48 ^d _e	51.20 ^b	63.27 _b	18.70 ^b	20.4 ₃ ^b	453.00 _a	463.65 _{bc}	195.82 _{bc}	263.01 ^a _b	
V ₈	Jaya	45.30 ^a _{bc}	47.97 _a	1.27 ^c	1.38 ^d	31.90 ^a	43.4 ₇ ^a	1.34 _c	1.67 ^e	32.2 ₃	35.1 ₇	8.57 ^c	10.00 _c	90.23 ^a	100.97 _{ab}	24.69 ^c _d	30.50 ^c	41.73 _c	7.43 ^c	9.73 ^c	381.49 _{ab}	406.37 _c	125.72 _{de}	157.10 _{bc}	
V ₉	GAR 22	49.67 ^c _d	52.10 _{ab}	1.07 ^a _b	1.17 ^{ab} _c	37.20 ^c	51.6 ₇ ^b	0.93 _a	1.21 ^a	33.1 ₃	36.3 ₃	9.57 ^{bc}	10.50 _c	122.40 ^d _e	135.40 _d	29.12 ^a	61.77 ^a _b	81.97 _a	20.00 ^a _b	22.6 ₀ ^b	183.40 _c	274.83 _d	153.48 _{cd}	238.84 ^a _{bc}	
V ₁₀	TN 1	55.03 ^d	58.27 _{bc}	1.26 ^c	1.41 ^d	46.07 ^d	57.8 ₇ ^c	1.35 _c	1.60 ^d _e	32.5 ₀	37.8 ₃	8.33 ^c	9.93 ^c	150.13 ^f	156.77 _e	29.64 ^a	10.63 ^d	16.53 _e	8.87 ^c	10.3 ₀ ^c	223.20 _c	271.25 _d	97.18 ^c	133.64 ^c	
SEm ±	V	1.88	1.91	0.05	0.06	1.21	1.72	0.05	0.06	2.55	2.26	0.43	0.43	4.72	4.51	0.79	5.95	3.81	1.98	1.45	25.29	27.14	16.15	34.68	
	Y	0.84	0.88	0.02	0.02	0.51	0.78	0.02	0.03	0.61	0.67	0.20	0.21	1.94	2.08	0.37	1.71	1.56	0.61	0.61	12.11	12.61	7.41	9.81	
	V × Y	3.26	2.77	0.06	0.08	1.62	2.47	0.07	0.08	1.94	2.13	0.63	0.65	6.13	6.57	1.17	5.40	4.92	1.93	1.88	38.28	39.88	23.38	31.03	
	CD at 5%	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	NS	NS	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	
	CV (%)	9.72	9.34	9.40	10.38	8.04	9.24	10.2 ₂	9.94	10.2 ₅	9.86	11.70	10.45	9.09	8.72	7.86	25.30	17.34	24.96	20.4 ₃	22.03	17.76	24.66	24.09	

Note: Treatment means with the letter(s) in common are not significant by DNMRT at 5% level of significance; Sig. - Significant; NS-Non-significant; DAT - Days after transplanting; Significant parameter and its interactions: Y

Table 3: Correlation of leaf folder infestation with morphological parameter of rice varieties (Pooled Kharif, 2021 and 2022)

Leaf folder and morphological traits	Leaf folder Leaf damage (%)		Leaf length (cm)		Leaf width (cm)		Flag leaf length (cm)		Flag leaf width (cm)		No. of leaves/hill		No. of tillers/hill		No. of trichomes/ cm ² leaf area				Trichome length (µm)				Plant height (cm)		Panicle length (cm)
	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial	Adaxial	Abaxial			
Crop growth stage/DAT	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	75
Leaf folder	45	1																							

length (µm)	Adaxia 1	75	-.711*	-.725*	-.625	-.623	-.411	-.390	-.512	-.700*	-.190	-.045	-.013	.257	.768*	.839*	.686*	.644*	.613	.630	.811*	1						
	Abaxia 1	45	-.786*	-.809*	-.486	-.532	-.521	-.480	-.393	-.570	-.419	-.281	-.020	.261	.860*	.878*	.833*	.824*	.860*	.880*	.663*	.885*	1					
		75	-.860*	-.869*	-.565	-.615	-.595	-.521	-.378	-.544	-.460	-.351	-.082	.175	.855*	.832*	.785*	.801*	.797*	.799*	.626	.824*	.945*	1				
Plant height (cm)		45	.389	.497	.795*	.877*	-.049	-.028	.708*	.851**	-.148	-.330	-.110	-.064	-.481	-.463	-.653*	-.564	-.427	-.475	-.673*	-.642*	-.563	-.505	1			
		75	.392	.514	.706*	.890*	-.218	-.227	.514	.763*	-.298	-.456	-.158	-.175	-.509	-.504	-.657*	-.539	-.481	-.520	-.682*	-.604	-.548	-.516	.942*	1		
Panicle length (cm)		75	-.012	.048	.731*	.656*	-.213	-.237	.744*	.831*	-.310	-.478	-.429	.333	-.230	-.231	-.093	.015	.081	.060	-.471	-.275	-.115	-.067	.642*	.576	1	

Note: * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 4: Biochemical content in leaf and stem of rice varieties (Kharif, 2021 and 2022)

Vr. No.	Varieties	Moisture (%)				Chlorophyll (mg/g)				Total phenol (%)				Total soluble sugars (%)				Total antioxidant activity (%)			
		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem	
		45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT	45 DAT	75 DAT
V ₁	GAR 1	73.52 ^a	71.57 ^a	65.24 ^a	65.83 ^a	2.49 ^a	2.20 ^a	2.46 ^a	2.34 ^b	0.39 ^{ab}	0.57 ^b	0.56 ^c	0.75 ^b	3.81 ^a	3.08 ^a	3.97 ^b	3.19 ^a	1.09 ^a	1.06 ^a	0.65 ^d	0.46 ^a
V ₂	GAR 14	72.65 ^a	72.03 ^a	65.87 ^a	66.86 ^a	2.16 ^a	2.00 ^a	2.13 ^a	2.02 ^{ab}	0.54 ^a	0.64 ^{ab}	0.61 ^{abc}	0.79 ^{ab}	3.71 ^a	2.87 ^a	3.52 ^{ab}	3.02 ^a	1.15 ^a	1.12 ^a	0.74 ^{bc}	0.49 ^a
V ₃	GR 101	71.11 ^a	68.14 ^a	66.49 ^a	62.55 ^a	2.03 ^a	1.92 ^a	1.86 ^a	1.95 ^a	0.57 ^a	0.68 ^a	0.66 ^a	0.86 ^a	3.34 ^a	2.43 ^a	3.32 ^a	2.76 ^a	1.14 ^a	1.15 ^a	0.77 ^{ab}	0.51 ^a
V ₄	Pankhali	81.39 ^b	79.54 ^b	75.11 ^b	75.72 ^b	5.15 ^b	4.32 ^b	4.51 ^b	3.67 ^{cd}	0.15 ^c	0.24 ^c	0.15 ^e	0.29 ^c	5.82 ^b	5.84 ^d	5.46 ^e	5.29 ^{bc}	0.68 ^e	0.51 ^b	0.21 ^g	0.14 ^b
V ₅	Krishna Kamod	81.68 ^b	80.57 ^b	75.91 ^b	75.85 ^b	5.20 ^b	4.15 ^b	4.36 ^b	3.47 ^{cd}	0.18 ^c	0.26 ^c	0.18 ^{de}	0.31 ^c	5.50 ^b	5.49 ^{bcd}	5.37 ^c	5.10 ^{bc}	0.72 ^{bc}	0.57 ^b	0.22 ^{fg}	0.17 ^b
V ₆	GR 11	80.14 ^b	78.46 ^b	75.18 ^b	74.26 ^b	5.04 ^b	3.91 ^b	4.01 ^b	3.39 ^c	0.22 ^{bc}	0.28 ^c	0.22 ^d	0.33 ^c	5.25 ^b	4.83 ^b	5.17 ^c	4.74 ^b	0.78 ^{bc}	0.61 ^b	0.28 ^{ef}	0.22 ^b
V ₇	GAR 13	72.56 ^a	69.51 ^a	66.52 ^a	63.26 ^a	2.44 ^a	2.14 ^a	2.41 ^a	2.13 ^{ab}	0.56 ^a	0.67 ^a	0.65 ^{ab}	0.83 ^{ab}	3.43 ^a	2.77 ^a	3.74 ^{ab}	3.15 ^a	1.19 ^a	1.13 ^a	0.83 ^a	0.55 ^a
V ₈	Jaya	79.65 ^b	78.42 ^b	75.26 ^b	73.74 ^b	5.00 ^b	3.79 ^b	3.88 ^b	3.34 ^c	0.25 ^{bc}	0.28 ^c	0.23 ^d	0.37 ^c	5.27 ^b	5.02 ^{bc}	5.62 ^c	5.51 ^c	0.81 ^b	0.62 ^b	0.30 ^e	0.23 ^b
V ₉	GAR 22	71.43 ^a	70.77 ^a	63.34 ^a	62.10 ^a	2.06 ^a	1.93 ^a	2.00 ^a	1.97 ^a	0.50 ^a	0.61 ^{ab}	0.59 ^{bc}	0.77 ^{ab}	3.46 ^a	2.80 ^a	3.48 ^{ab}	2.88 ^a	1.11 ^a	1.07 ^a	0.68 ^{cd}	0.47 ^a
V ₁₀	TN 1	81.89 ^b	81.95 ^b	75.21 ^b	75.33 ^b	5.29 ^b	4.48 ^b	4.71 ^b	3.78 ^d	0.21 ^{bc}	0.27 ^c	0.19 ^{de}	0.32 ^c	5.65 ^b	5.55 ^{cd}	5.41 ^c	5.18 ^{bc}	0.70 ^{bc}	0.57 ^b	0.22 ^{fg}	0.16 ^b
SEm±	V	1.69	1.67	1.52	1.61	0.18	0.28	0.25	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.23	0.21	0.19	0.19	0.04	0.09	0.02	0.04
	Y	0.83	0.76	0.71	0.73	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.10	0.11	0.09	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01
	V × Y	2.63	2.41	2.25	2.32	0.30	0.21	0.25	0.20	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.29	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.02
CD at 5%	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
CV (%)	5.95	5.56	5.53	5.78	11.64	9.71	10.98	9.96	12.99	14.14	11.60	13.22	12.30	13.31	11.33	12.34	9.60	11.84	9.40	11.32	

Note: Treatment means with the letter(s) in common are not significant by DNMRT at 5% level of significance; Sig.- Significant; Significant parameter and its interactions: Y, V × Y for chlorophyll

Table 5: Correlation of leaf folder infestation with biochemical traits of leaf and stem of rice varieties (Pooled Kharif, 2021 and 2022)

Leaf folder leaf damage (%) and biochemical traits	Crop growth stage/DAT	Leaf folder Leaf damage (%)		Moisture (%)				Chlorophyll (mg/g)				Total soluble sugar (%)				Total phenol (%)				Antioxidant activity (%)			
		45	75	Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem		Leaf		Stem	
				45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75	45	75		
Leaf folder	45	1																					

